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Performance of commercial rice varieties in lowlands of western Venezuela

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We evaluated the response of rice varieties Cimarron, Araure 4, Oryzica 3, Oryzica 1, Oryzica Llanos 5, and La Toma to increasing N levels. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with varieties in the main plots and N levels in subplots during the 1993 wet season.

Soil was an Inceptisol with 4.7% organic matter, pH 5.8, 10 ppm P, 147 ppm K, and 53.4% clay content in the upper 17 cm. Rice was dry seeded at 160 kg/ha in a farmer's field. Half of the N dose, 20.2 kg P/ha as P₂O₅, and 49.8 kg K/ha as K₂O were broadcast and incorporated into the soil at sowing. The other half of the N dose was applied at panicle

Grain and milling yield and yield components of 6 commercial rice varieties.^a Guanare, Venezuela. 1993 wet season.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Head rice (%)	Broken grain (%)	Panicles/m ² (no.)	Grains/panicle (no.)	1,000-grain weight (g)
Oryzica 3	5.3 a	57.5 ab	6.7 cd	224.2 bc	126.0 a	19.8 c
Oryzica Llanos 5	5.2 ab	59.7 a	4.5 e	233.6 bc	80.4 c	28.2 a
Araure 4	4.8 bc	58.8 ab	5.2 de	240.0 abc	80.0 c	25.4 b
La Toma	4.6 cd	56.8 b	7.6 c	245.3 ab	105.0 b	18.1 c
Cimarron	3.9 e	51.1 c	16.1 a	263.6 a	62.0 cd	24.5 b
Oryzica 1	3.6 e	56.9 ab	9.9 b	215.6 c	70.0 cd	23.7 b
CV (%)	14.1	5.6	7.9	12.3	16.0	9.7

^aNumbers in a column followed by the same letter are not different according to LSD test at P = 0.05.

initiation. Rice was sown on 31 Mar and the first irrigation was on 1 Apr. The field was flooded on 8 May and the water level was kept at 20 cm until harvest. Cimarron and Oryzica 1 were harvested on 6 Aug, Oryzica 3 and La Toma on 16 Aug, and Araure 4 and Oryzica Llanos 5 on 20 Aug.

Oryzica 3 and Oryzica Llanos 5 produced the highest grain yields (see

table), rice grain yield response increased up to 120 kg N/ha. Oryzica Llanos 5 produced the highest head rice yield, lowest % broken grains, and highest grain weight. Oryzica 3 produced the most grains/panicle. Araure 4 lodged severely.

Pyricularia grisea, *Helminthosporium oryzae*, *Cercospora oryzae*, and *Ustilago indica virens* affected Cimarron and Oryzica 1. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

Three rice varieties of medium duration released for rainfed lowland areas in Cambodia

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Cambodia grows rainfed lowland rice of medium duration on about 30% of its area. Popular varieties of medium duration are usually weakly photoperiod sensitive with less than 150 d duration. No recommended modern varieties of medium duration were previously available in the country, so a massive varietal introduction and testing program was initiated in 1989. More than 11,000 introduced and indigenous varieties were tested during 1989-92 using a multi-locational approach and a four-tier testing system: observational yield trials, preliminary yield trials, advanced yield trials, and on-farm adaptive trials (OFAT).

Three varieties performed very well and were released in 1992 as Santepheap

Table 1. Yield (t/ha) of Santepheap 1, Santepheap 2, and Santepheap 3 compared with that of checks in varietal trials in Cambodia. 1989-92.

Variety	Year (no. of locations)			
	1989 (3)	1990 (15)	1991 (17)	1992 (87)
Santepheap 1	5.0 a ^a	3.5 b	4.0 b	2.7 ± 0.22
Santepheap 2	4.0 c	4.1 a	3.9 b	3.1 ± 0.27
Santepheap 3	4.8 b	3.5 b	4.2 a	3.2 ± 0.21
Check (IR42, locals)	3.1 d	3.1 c	3.5 c	2.6 ± 0.22
CV (%)	9.0	12.0	11.3	-

^aValues with a common letter in the same column are not significantly different by DMRT.

Table 2. Main characteristics of the recommended rice varieties.

Characteristic	Santepheap 1	Santepheap 2	Santepheap 3
Duration (d)	131 WS ^a	135 WS	137 WS
Height (cm)	108	108	106
Vegetative vigor score	4	3	4
Panicle length (cm)	24	24	24
Grains per panicle (no.)	110	102	105
100-grain weight (g)	2.7	2.7	2.5
Grain size (L×B in mm)	6.8 × 2.2	6.8 × 2.2	6.1 × 2.6
Grain type ^b	LS	LS	LB
Leafhopper damage score	4	2	3
Gall midge damage score	6	6	5
BPH reaction ^c	R	R	R
GLH reaction ^c	R	R	R
Tungro reaction ^c	MR	MR	R
Blast reaction ^c	MR	MR	MR
Phenotypic acceptability	4	4	3

^aWS = weakly photoperiod sensitive. ^bLS = long slender, LB = long bold. ^cR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant.